

ENERGY ABSORPTION BEHAVIOUR OF 3-D-WOVEN SANDWICH STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

In the last years a new kind of sandwich structures basing on 3D woven fibre preforms has been developed. The unique feature of this material is the integral connection of the woven skins by a z-directional pile-fibre system. This concept allows an easy manufacturing of highly damage tolerant light-weight structural panels. Within the BRITE/EURAM-Project "AFICOSS" suitable manufacturing techniques have been developed, the basic material behaviour has been studied experimentally and theoretically and exemplary components for several application fields have been realised and evaluated. Investigations of the energy absorbing behaviour of this new material respectively the development of crash-elements with optimised crash behaviour, were realised.

INTRODUCTION

In this paper a study of the energy absorption behaviour of 3D woven sandwich elements is presented including the development of suitable testing methods allowing the reproducible and application-relevant evaluation of the material behaviour. The study is focused to the application of the results to a prototype of an absorbing element used by aerospace industry. In order to save total weight in addition to be economically competitive, present energy absorber device shall be replaced by other made of advanced composite materials. The main function of a crash absorber is to avoid damages towards the rest of the structure, and damages in a structure are most of times related to deformation energy, then it is necessary to fit up the structure with a mechanism which be able to absorb the deformation energy. Some requirements should be satisfied, a minimum load level below the structure must not suffer any kind of damage; a maximum load level before failure initiation of the energy absorber start, in such way that maximum load during crash remains always below this level; and a quantity of absorbed energy, which depends on the maintenance of a high crash load and a large crash displacement.

AFICOSS; A BRITE/EURAM PROJECT

In AFICOSS, 8 partners from 5 European countries work together on the development of Advanced Fabrics for Integral Composite Sandwich Structures: Parabeam, Hexcel, Dasa, Metalleido, Bremen, Intermarine, Katholieke Universiteit Leuven & University of Zaragoza.

The AFICOSS project was defined to develop the technology and its applications. The Integral Composite Sandwich Structures in AFICOSS consist of 3D-fabric impregnated with polymer resin. The result is a sandwich structure where top and bottom layers are completely integrated with core. Consequently these structures combine the well know advantages of a sandwich construction (lightweight yet very strong & stiff) with some unique characteristics not found in most other sandwich structures:

- high damage tolerance, high residual strength after impact.
- extremely high delamination resistance (up to 4 times that a conventional high performance sandwich structures.
- capacity to contain functional foams such as phenolic foams resulting in durable fire-proof / smoke-free structural panels that can be applied in train carriages or submarines.
- high and well-distributed energy absorption which can be exploited in structural crash absorbing elements.
- potential for cost-effective semi-continuous production of Integral Composite Sandwich Panels or ICSP®'s.

3D WOVEN SANDWICH STRUCTURES.

The advanced fabrics in AFICOSS are 3-dimensional fabrics (3D-fabrics) manufactured by prime partner Parabeam. The 3D-fabric consist of two layers, connected by orthogonal threads, resulting in a textile sandwich preform. The production of 3D-fabric is based on velvet weaving technology. Velvet is produced by cutting the connecting threads between the two fabric layers of a 3D-fabric. When circumstances for European velvet woven companies were deteriorating, alternative applications of the technology were sought. Based on strategic market research and analysis that indicated several attractive potential markets, Parabeam shifted its activities from velvet towards glassfibre 3D-fabrics for use as reinforcement in composites.

DESCRIPTION OF 3D WOVEN SANDWICH STRUCTURES

Figure 1. Schematical drawing of 3D fabric.

Figure 2. 3D-fabric view in warp and weft direction.

APPLICATION: SUBFLOOR OF A HELICOPTER.

The subfloor of a helicopter is responsible for the energy absorption being necessary to avoid injury of the passengers after a crash from low flight height. This can happen after an engine failure in ground-near flight-operation when autorotation is not possible.

The principle design of a helicopter subfloor is shown in figure 4. The sandwich-based construction is necessary because fuel and various electrical equipment has to be placed in the subfloor. Up to now sandwich panels with honeycomb core or sine-wave-beams are used as structural panels. The problem is, that the sandwich panels do not offer a sufficient energy absorbing behaviour and the sine-wave beams are very expensive in manufacturing and high energy absorption. Figure 3, shows various concepts for energy absorbing structures basing on 3D panels. For the helicopter subfloor concept 3.2. has been chosen. To enable a good energy absorption a special triggering device has been developed leading to a cutting of the pile fibres. The failure mechanism is demonstrated in figure 5.

The next task was the development of T- and X-shaped sandwich elements based on 3D sandwich structures. One possibility is to start from dry fabrics stitched together to complex perform and impregnate them afterwards in special tools. This concepts leads to very light elements with high structural integrity after crash. On the other hand the manufacturing is very time consuming and the tools are very expensive. Therefore another root has been followed up basing on pre-consolidated sandwich panels which are connected by additional aluminium connecting elements. Figure 6 and 7 shows typical structures before and after crash test.

Figure 3. Concepts for energy absorbing structures.

Figure 4. Design of a helicopter subfloor.

Figure 5. Demonstration of failure mechanism.

Figures 6 and 7. Typical structures before and after crash test.

MATERIAL BEHAVIOUR

The energy absorbers are usually composed by several types of materials due to the necessity to have some requirements to be reached. Brittle fibre-reinforced composites exhibits exclusively transverse shearing and lamina bending crushing modes, but ductile fibre-reinforced composite materials never show these modes. Local buckling crushing mode can be exhibited by both ductile and brittle composites. A combination of the transverse shearing and lamina bending crushing modes can be exhibited by brittle fibre-reinforced composite structures. Influence of material (resins & fibres), specimen geometry, 2D-Fabric composition, pile orientation, velocity of the mechanism and triggering device have been taking into account during the design stage.

Figure 8. Crushing process of fibre-reinforced composite structures

3D-FABRIC FOR ENERGY ABSORBERS

Several designs of the energy absorber model were studied in order to optimise collapse of the structure with multiple objective of finding a geometrical relation of triggering device which offered a stress-strain acceptable behaviour, appropriate material composition in order to assure: specific energy absorption quantity required, a stable crushing process and a determined maintained load level. Summarising the more important design variables which were used: geometry of triggering device, material parameters for skins (material, number, fabric-type) and piles (material, length, density, orientation), resin properties and inclusion or not of foam.

One of the important steps was the design of the triggering device in order to adjust the energy absorbing behaviour according to the requirements. Theoretical simulations and testing series led to the geometry shown in Fig.9. With this configuration it was possible to reach exactly the required crash force of 30 N/mm and maintain it over a displacement of 100% of the panel height. The idea was to generate a continuous failure by cutting the pile fibres and bending the skins by using a special triggering device, obtaining an optimum force-displacement curve without load-peaks and high displacements to achieve a high energy absorption avoiding buckling of the structure.

Figure 9. Energy absorber model used for 3D-Fabrics.

NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF CRASH BEHAVIOUR.

The numerical simulation of energy absorbers was carried out by means finite element computer codes. Models were calculated in vectorized and multi-tasked mainframe supercomputers, e.g. CONVEX and HP. Several software packages were used for numerical crash simulations, explicit finite elements programs with interactive graphic meshing pre-processor and interactive graphic results post-processing. Numerical simulations allows to obtain new and before hard to get, high priced or impossible to reach results such as the detailed crash energy absorption histories of individual components. Moreover, descriptive pictures of particular and combined failure modes, the detailed history of the process, impossible to be noticed by human eyes or high-speed cameras.

Programs chosen for this task were DYNA3D and ABAQUS. However, the analysis of composite materials is limited because the modelization of laminated plates is considered only by a homogenisation procedure. Furthermore, a fracture law for dynamic processes is missing. These obstacles can be overcome since both codes are an open system and therefore manipulations of the source code by the user can be done easily.

Figure 10. Crash simulation sequence for the final configuration.

An important parameter was the design and calculation of crash initiators in order to obtain the desired force-displacement curve. The typical load-displacement curve for 3D-fabrics without any failure initiator showed a initial high load and a radical loss of maintained load. Inclusion of a load limiting failure initiator at one of the ends led to a reduction of the initial load-peak and enhanced the post failure performance. Triggering devices were included in order to obtain the best maintained load and a progressive crash behaviour.

Figure 11. Typical force-displacement curve obtained with numerical calculations

EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION OF ENERGY ABSORPTION BEHAVIOUR

In an experimental program the basic crash elements have been optimised with regard to fabric material, matrix type, foam and triggering device. In order to characterise the behaviour as well quasi-static test and crash tests with velocities up to 10 m/s have been performed. On important result was, that the crash-behaviour is not highly influenced by the crash speed.

It has been shown, that the adjustment of triggering device geometry and sandwich material is most important to enable a controlled failure behaviour on high load level up to a high displacement. With the help of a high speed video camera and the results of the FE-computer simulations an optimum configuration with load uniformities of 1, maximum displacements of 100% and weight specific energy absorption of more than 20 KJ/Kg has been developed. These values are indications for a very good energy absorption behaviour demonstrating the high potential of this material for realising subfloor elements.

Orienting crash test have been performed with sandwich panels in T-shaped configuration. Pre-consolidated foamed panels have been glued together by aluminium connecting elements. The specimen after the crash test are shown in figure 7, the force displacement is shown in figure 12. The curve demonstrates that also on sub-component level a very good energy absorption behaviour is possible. The failure is continuous and exactly on the required load level for the helicopter subfloor application.

Figure 12. Experimental curve force-displacement.

CONCLUSIONS

3D woven sandwich structures have been found to be a structural material with very interesting mechanical properties. Especially if damage tolerance or energy absorption are of importance they offer a higher potential for realising light weight structural components than conventional sandwich structures with foam or honeycomb core.

In combination with a special triggering device, leading to a cutting of pile fibres, it was possible to realise sandwich panels with very interesting energy absorbing behaviour and high weight specific energy absorption. Also T- and X-shape combinations of sandwich panels, being for example typical for helicopter subfloor structures, have been realised and successfully tested.

In parallel to the experimental work, calculation techniques on the basis of the Finite Elements have been developed in order to simulate the material crash behaviour compares qualitatively

very well with the experimental results. For a quantitative calculation the influence of basic effects like non-linear material behaviour or friction between sandwich and triggering device have to be taken into account.

Numerical simulations can be compared with experimental results. The same testing conditions were used during the experimental testing and the results proved the powerful and usefulness of these numerical tools. Numerical tools help us to reduce number of expensive experimental test. An interesting result of all crash test was, that the material behaviour is nearly independent of the testing velocity. This fact is of big advantage for the optimum design of crash elements.

The experimental results show, that 3D sandwich structures have a high potential for a cost effective manufacturing of energy absorbing structural components. The specific design and the high number of material parameters allows the optimisation of stiffness, strength and failure modes according to the requirements of the applications. The through-penetration energy is very high, if thick fabrics with low shear stiffness (un-foamed) are used, because then big panel areas are damaged by consuming energy.

The damaged area after through-penetration can be reduced to the area of the impactor without delaminations, if foamed 3D-sandwiches are used. This reduces structural degradation and repair costs. Box-like crash elements with good crash behaviour and high weight specific energy absorption of more than 30KJ/Kg can be realised. Panel-like crash-elements with good energy absorption behaviour without risk of rapid failure due to buckling can be realised. On the other hand, the potential for easy one-step manufacturing can not be utilised fully because in most cases additional pre-manufactured layers have to be adhered on the 3D fabric in a second step.

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